

THE IMPORTANCE OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL STAFF

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Abstract. *This article describes the general rules, principles, technology, structure of distance education in the system of continuous professional development of pedagogical personnel.*

Keywords: *distance education, technology, professional development, educational technologies, information technologies.*

Introduction. Today, engineering, technology, and production are developing in close connection with the education system. Due to the progress achieved in these areas, new directions appear in the educational system, the content of teaching is improved, new types of education are formed, and modern methods are based. is formed according to its relevance and is becoming more and more popular.

According to Article 16 of the Law of the Legislative Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan LRU-637 dated September 23, 2020 "On Education" by students in accordance with distance education curricula and training programs aimed at obtaining the necessary knowledge, qualifications and skills remotely using information and communication technologies and the Internet global information network.[1]

In accordance with this law, it is the main reason for the development of distance training processes in our country, and it leads to great importance being attached to it. Distance learning provides an opportunity for all those who want to learn to continuously improve their skills.

The training system is an additional pedagogical education that is carried out as a prerequisite for the development of the educational system. It is almost impossible to adapt to any changes in the educational system without prior training of pedagogic personnel. Any innovation in education affects the system of training of pedagogic personnel and requires a professional understanding of the basic values in the content, forms, and methods of training. Therefore, in the process of improving the quality of the education system in our country, the problem of improving the qualifications of deaf pedagogues is the most urgent.

The development of the system of continuous professional development of pedagogical personnel includes constant updating and flexible response to the requirements of the modern labor market. This, in turn, creates conditions for the formation of the personal success of each participant of this process. taking into account the trends, the innovative development of the educational system implies the use of distance learning technologies in the methodology of continuous professional development. Therefore, the problem of professional development of pedagogic personnel through alternative forms remains very urgent. One of these forms is distance training, which to some extent provides solutions to the current problems of additional pedagogical education, namely:

- An opportunity to improve the professional qualifications of a large number of pedagogues;

-Fast and quality training of pedagogues to manage innovative processes resulting from modernization of education;

- Possibility of training without separation from the main workplace and direct use of the acquired knowledge in professional activities;

- Implementation of the principles of individualization and differentiation of education;

-Reducing the cost of training by reducing the costs of travel and replacement of pedagogic personnel.

Distance training cannot completely replace the traditional form of training, because there is no direct contact between the teacher and the students, but it already has a certain knowledge. perfect for those who have and want to improve their skills.

Distance learning

The process of distance training consists of several modules. According to the lesson schedule (synchronously), each student receives a set of materials for the next module through the platform. These materials are in the form of a theoretical part, a practical part and a series of tasks. The theoretical part contains basic information, ideas, and examples that the listeners can rely on to perform their tasks.

During distance training, students perform tasks and develop scenarios of educational, creative, problem situations. Distance learning is an effective alternative to face-to-face training courses if it is based on the following methods:

-modular system of educational organization including theoretical and practical parts developed on the basis of heuristic (special) educational principles;

- availability of openness to discuss materials sent by listeners.

The training process based on distance learning technologies includes both mandatory classroom training and independent work of students. The participation of the teacher in the educational process is determined not only by conducting audience training, but also by the need to constantly support the educational and cognitive activity of the audience by conducting network classes and consultations. [3]

Information technologies used in distance education can be divided into three groups:

- technologies for providing educational information;

- educational information transfer technologies;

- educational data storage and processing technologies.

Together, the above technologies constitute distance education. At the same time, in the implementation of educational programs, mainly the educational process and the educational information transfer technologies that support it are of particular importance.

Education and information technologies in distance learning

Educational technology is a set of didactic methods and techniques used to deliver educational information from its source to the consumer and depends on the form of its presentation.

The most adapted educational technologies used in distance education include video lectures, multimedia lectures and laboratory seminars, electronic multimedia textbooks, test systems, simulation models, computer simulators, counseling and tests using telecommunication tools, video conferences.

Information technology is based on the use of computer technologies, storing and processing educational information, delivering it to the audience, providing interactive interaction

of the audience with the teacher or pedagogical software, as well as testing the audience's knowledge. transfer hardware and software.

In the process of continuous professional development, information technology itself is not important, but how much its use serves to achieve educational goals. The choice of communication tools should be determined not by technology, but by content. This means that the choice of technologies should be based on the study of the content of training courses, the required level of activity of the students, their involvement in the learning process, specific goals and expected learning results, etc. The outcome of distance education depends not on the type of communication and information technology, but on the quality of course development and delivery.

At the same time, the development of comprehensive modular programs of continuous education through distance learning technologies provides an individual educational direction of students. The reason is that the system of credit accumulation is currently being implemented in the field of education.

Conclusion

The modular construction in the system of professional development of pedagogic personnel gives each trainee the opportunity to make an independent choice, individual motivation and self-evaluation of the result. Aimed at increasing professional development in the creation of distance education programs includes the mechanism of the system's response to external changes. The use of distance education technologies in the process of pedagogical professional development improves the professional knowledge of pedagogues throughout life, including meeting the educational and professional needs of people. provides continuous improvement.

REFERENCES

1. [LEX.UZ - O'zbekiston qonunchiligi](#) O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qonunchilik ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi.
2. Агапова О.В., Вершловский С.Г., Тоскина Н.А. Уроки для взрослых: Пособие для тех, кто работает в системе образования взрослых. – СПб.: КАРО, 2008. –176 с.
3. Андреев А.А., Солдаткин В.И. Дистанционное обучение: сущность, технология, организация. – М.: Издательство МЭСИ. 1999. –С. 196.
4. Begimkulov U.Sh. Pedagogik ta'lim jarayonlarini axborotlashtirishni tashkil etish va boshqarish nazariyasi va amaliyoti. Pedagogika fanlari doktori ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan dissertatsiya. – T., 2007. –305-b.
5. Boltaev B.J. va boshqalar. Informatika va hisoblash texnikasi asoslari. / Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarining 9-sinf uchun darslik. – T.: «Cho'lpon», 2011. –144-b.
6. Pedagogik atamalar lug'ati. / Tuzuvchilar Djuraev R.X. va boshqalar. – T.: «Fan», 2008. – 195-b.
7. Педагогический энциклопедический словарь. / Гл. ред Б.М.Бим-Бад. – М.: «Большая Российская энциклопедия». 2003. –С. 528.
8. Полат Е.С., Бухаркина М.Ю., Моисеева М.В. Теория и практика дистанционного обучения. Учеб. пособие. – М: ОИЦ «Академия». 2004. –С. 416.